

**BOSHLANG‘ICH SINIF O‘QUVCHILARINI O‘QISH SAVODXONLIGINI
RIVOJLANTIRISHDA MULTIMEDIYA VOSITALARIDAN FOYDALANISH
METODIKASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH**

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***Annotatsiya.** Ushbu maqola hozirgi kunning asosiy ta’lim vositalariga aylanayotgan multimediya va texnologiyalardan boshlang‘ich sinf o‘quvchilariga sifatli ta’lim berishda va o‘qitishda foydalanish va uning ta’lim samaradorligini oshirishdagi o‘rni haqida foydali bilimlarni qamrab oladi. Ta’limda multimediya vositalaridan foydalanish metodikasini eng yaxshi usulda takomillashtirish o‘quvchilarda darslarga bo‘lgan qiziqishni oshiribgina qolmay, ularning dunyoqarashini yanada kengaytirishda va albatta, kelgusida jahon andozalariga javob beraoladigan raqobatbardosh kadr bo‘lishlariga yordam berishini bilib olamiz.*

***Kalit so‘zlar:** samaradorlik, multimediya, kommunikativlik, o‘quv material, zamonviy pedagog va texnologiyalar.*

**IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF USING MULTIMEDIA IN THE
DEVELOPMENT OF READING LITERACY OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS**

***Abstract.** This article covers useful knowledge about the use of multimedia and technologies, which are becoming the main educational tools of today, in quality education and training of primary school students and its role in improving educational efficiency. We will learn that improving the method of using multimedia tools in education in the best way will not only increase students' interest in lessons, but also help them to expand their worldview and, of course, to become competitive personnel who can meet world standards in the future.*

***Key words:** efficiency, multimedia, communicative, educational material, modern pedagogue and technologies.*

**СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕТОДИКИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ
МУЛЬТИМЕДИЙНЫХ СРЕДСТВ В РАЗВИТИИ ЧИТАТЕЛЬНОЙ
ГРАМОТНОСТИ УЧАЩИХСЯ НАЧАЛЬНЫХ КЛАССОВ**

***Аннотация.** В данной статье представлены полезные знания об использовании мультимедиа и технологий, которые сегодня становятся основными образовательными*

инструментами, в качественном образовании и обучении учащихся начальных классов и их роли в повышении эффективности образования. Мы узнаем, что совершенствование метода использования мультимедийных средств в образовании наилучшим образом не только повысит интерес учащихся к урокам, но и поможет им расширить свое мировоззрение и, конечно же, стать конкурентоспособными кадрами, способными соответствовать мировым стандартам в сфере образования. будущее.

Ключевые слова: *эффективность, мультимедиа, коммуникативность, учебный материал, современный педагог и технологии.*

Bugungi kunda dunyoning shiddat bilan globallashuvi ko'pchilik kasb egalari singari o'qituvchilarni ham rivojlanishga, o'z ustida ishlashga undaydi. Shunday ekan boshlang'ich ta'lim samaradorligini oshirish, bolalarga fanni sevishga va qiziqib o'rganishga yordam beradigan turli metodlarni yaratishda turli multimediya vositalaridan va texnologiyalardan foydalanish pedagoglarning asosiy vazifalaridan biri hisoblanadi.

Bugungi kunda Prezidentimiz jahon standartlariga javob bera oladigan kadrlar yetishtirish maqsadida boshlang'ich ta'limga alohida e'tibor bermoqdalar. Buni Prezidentimizning 2022-yil 28- yanvardagi "2022-2026- yillarga mo'ljallangan Yangi O'zbekistonning Taraqqiyot strategiyasi to'g'risida" gi PF-60 Farmonidan ham anglashimiz mumkin. [4]

Hozirgi kunda o'quvchilarni metodlarimizda qo'llaniladigan tarqatma meteriallari emas, balki turli g'ariyibotlarga boy, rang-barang multimediali videodarslar va electron bajariladigan quiz testlar qiziqtiradi. Texnologiyalarning rivojlanishi va dars metodlarini multimediyali qilib takomillashtirish orqali o'quvchilarning dunyoqarashini o'stirishimiz, fikrlash tezligini ortib borishimizda katta ahamiyatga ega. Mana shunday zamonaviy texnologiyalarga asoslangan metodikani takomillashtirish uchun asosan darslarda ko'proq multimediyalardan foydalanish, qiziqarli videolar orqali tayyorlangan metodikalardan foydalanish maqsadga muvofiqdir. Bunday metodlarni takomillashtirish uchun avvalo, tilimizga allaqachon tanilib ulgurgan so'zlarning ma'nosini chuqurroq bilib olsak: multimedia atamasining bir qancha ma'nolari mavjud. Jumladan: multimedia-(inglizcha-yunoncha "multi"-ko'p, "media"-muhit) bu axborot informatsiya uzatishning xilma-xil vositalarini qamrab olgan texnologiya bo'lib, unda muayyan dasturlar va vositalar mavjud.

Multimedia- kompyuter tizimida matn, tovush, videotasvirni va turli animatsiyalarni mujassamlashtirish imkonini beruvchi zamonaviy axborotlar texnologiyasidir. Darslarda multimedia vositalaridan foydalanish jarayonida o'quvchi :

-o'quv materialini ko'rgazmali tarzda taqdim etadi;

-yangi materiallarni tezlik bilan yetkazadi;

-axborotlar tezligi va hajmini animatsiyalar yordamida boshqara oladi

Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining diqqatining buzilishi juda tez bo'lganligi sababli dars jarayonini qiziqarli metodlardan foydalanib darsni foydali bilimlarga boy va e'tiborni tortadigan qilib o'tishda multimediya vositalarining o'rni juda katta. Quyida ularning bir nechtasini darsda qanday foydalanishi bilan birga ko'rib o'tamiz:

1.Raqamli hikoya qiluvchilar: O'qituvchilar multimediya vositalaridan raqamli (electron) , rasmi, videoli va audioli electron hikoyalarni yaratishda foydalana olishadi va bu yosh o'quvchilarning til ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.[2]

2.Interaktiv doskalar: bunday doskalardan ta'limiy videolar ko'rsatishda, interaktiv (ikki tomonlama faoliyat, yoki bir-biriga ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi") o'yinlar va boshqa kontentlarni bolalarning o'qish jarayonida ko'rish uchun foydalanish mumkin. Shu o'rinda interaktiv o'yinlarning bolalarga yaxshi ta'siri haqida qo'shimcha qilsak: bu turdagi o'yinlar foydalanuvchilarga biror narsani bajarish, mantiqiy muammolarni hal qilish yoki faollikni bajarish imkonini beradi.

3.Ta'limiy ilovalar: Hozirgi kunda yosh o'rganuvchilar uchun turli xil ta'limiy ilovalar juda ham ko'p. Bunday animatsiyali, audioli ilovalar bolalarning o'rganish jarayonini yanada qiziqarli qiladi.

4.Virtual sayohatlar: bu yangi bilmagan joylarni kashf qilishning zamonaviy va osson usuli. Virtual sayohat orqali biz o'quvchilar bilan birgalikda xonani tark etmay turib tarixiy hodisalar, o'rmonlar va tabiat haqida juda ko'p bilimlarga ega bo'lishimiz mumkin.

Xulosa qilib aytadigan bo'lsak, boshlang'ich sinflarda samaradorlikni oshirishning eng yaxshi usuli bu texnologiyalardan va multimediyalardan foydalanish metodikasini takomillashtirishdir. Biz ona tili darslarimizda ham ingliz tilida qo'llaniladigan tinglab tushunish metodikalarini qo'llab, o'quvchilarimizda tushunish ko'nikmasini yana ham rivojlantirishimiz mumkin.

REFERENCES

1. Azixodjayeveva N.N Pedagogik texnologiya va pedagogik mahorat-T:Fan, 2006
2. Nurmatov,Z. O, Tursunpulatova, K. A, & Nasriddinova, Z. N (2023, May). THE ROLE OF MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. In international Conference on Science, Engeenering & Technology (Vol. 1, No.1, pp. 99-103)

3. S. Karimova and Sh. Habibullayeva .The Role and importance of “NATURAL SCIENCES” in the development of understanding of nature in general secondary schools. *Rising Flowers of Uzbekistan USA*. Amazon
4. Qayumova, S. (2022). БЎЛАЖАК БОСШЛАНҒИЧ СИНФ ЎҚИТУВСЧИЛАРИНИ TIMSS ХАЛҚАРО БАҲОЛАШ ДАСТУРИ АСОСИДА МЕТОДИК ТАЙЁРГАРЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА МУЛТИМЕДИЯ ВОСИТАЛАРИНИНГ ЎРНИ. *Science and innovation*, 1(B4), 159-162.
5. Shohsanam, K. (2023). THEORETICAL IMPORTANCE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE. *Science and innovation*, 2(Special Issue 3), 159-162.
6. Kayumova, S. T. qizi, Sharipov , S. R., Abdullayev , K. A. ugli, & Nurmatov , I. S. (2023). THE THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF IMPROVING STUDENTS’ READING PROFICIENCY BASED ON MODERN TRENDS. *RESEARCH AND EDUCATION*, 2(12), 57–61.
7. To‘lqin qizi Kayumova, S., Sharipov, S. R., ugli Abdullayev, K. A., & Nurmatov, I. S. (2023). THE THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF IMPROVING STUDENTS'READING PROFICIENCY BASED ON MODERN TRENDS. *RESEARCH AND EDUCATION*, 2(12), 57-61.
8. Kayumova, S. T. K. (2022). DIFFERENCES BETWEEN PISA AND TIMSS INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT PROGRAM. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(NUU Conference 2), 753-757.
9. Sh. Kayumova (2023). DIDACTIC PRINCIPLES FOR DEVELOPING NATIVE LANGUAGE AND READING LITERACY OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS. *Science and innovation*, 2 (B9), 57-60. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8348958
10. Sh. Kayumova (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' READING LITERACY THROUGH TRIZ PEDAGOGY. *Science and innovation*, 2 (B10), 157-160. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8433398
11. Qayumova, S. (2022). БЎЛАЖАК БОСШЛАНҒИЧ СИНФ ЎҚИТУВСЧИЛАРИНИ TIMSS ХАЛҚАРО БАҲОЛАШ ДАСТУРИ АСОСИДА МЕТОДИК ТАЙЁРГАРЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА МУЛТИМЕДИЯ ВОСИТАЛАРИНИНГ ЎРНИ. *Science and innovation*, 1(B4), 159-162.
12. Shahriddinovna, K. S. (2023). Didactic Features Of Development Of Nature Perception Skills Of Primary School Students. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 19, 183-187.

13. Shahriddinova, K. S. (2023). INTRODUCING CHILDREN OF PRIMARY SCHOOL AGE WITH THE WORLD. *American Journal of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(06), 09-14.
14. Shahriddinova K. S. Didactic Features Of Development Of Nature Perception Skills Of Primary School Students //Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching. – 2023. – T. 19. – C. 183-187.
15. Shahriddinova K. S. INTRODUCING CHILDREN OF PRIMARY SCHOOL AGE WITH THE WORLD //American Journal of Applied Science and Technology. – 2023. – T. 3. – №. 06. – C. 09-14.
16. Karimova, S. (2022). THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF" NATURAL SCIENCES" IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF UNDERSTANDING OF NATURE IN GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS. *Science and innovation*, 1(B6), 214-218.
17. Karimova S. THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF" NATURAL SCIENCES" IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF UNDERSTANDING OF NATURE IN GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS //Science and innovation. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. B6. – C. 214-218.
18. Karimova S. CHARACTERISTICS OF NATURAL TEACHING METHODOLOGY //Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. – 2021. – T. 1. – №. 11. – C. 737-740.
19. Karimova, S., & Ashurova, M. (2023). TYPES OF EDUCATION. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(8), 161–163. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/22537>
20. Mamatova, X., Karimova, S., & Turg'unboyeva, M. (2023). EDUCATION IS UPBRINGING, KNOWLEDGE IS SALVATION. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(8), 164–166. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/22538>
21. Mamatova , . H., Karimova, S., & Mamayusupova, . Z. (2023). PEDAGOGICAL ANALYSIS IN THE WORKS OF ALISHER NAVOI. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 5–8. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/23865>
22. Karimova S., Habibullayeva S. THE ESSENCE OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN PEDAGOGY //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 1. – C. 40-44.
23. Karimova Sevara Shaxriddin Qizi. (2023). FORMATION OF NATURE AWARENESS SKILLS OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *International Scientific and Current*

Research Conferences, 1(01), 43–45. Retrieved from
<https://www.orientalpublication.com/index.php/iscrc/article/view/1105>

24. Mamatova H., Karimova S., Mamayusupova Z. PEDAGOGICAL ANALYSIS IN THE WORKS OF ALISHER NAVOI //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 9. – C. 5-8.
25. Sevara, K., & Maftuna, S. (2024, February). BOSHLANG ‘ICH SINFLARDA ONA TILI DARSLARIGA QO ‘YILGAN ZAMONAVIY TALABLARNING XUSUSIYATI VA AHAMIYAT. In *International conference on multidisciplinary science* (Vol. 2, No. 2, pp. 65-67).
26. Sevara, K., & Mahliyo, X. (2024, February). BOSHLANG‘ICH SINFLARDA O‘QUVCHILARIDA MATEMATIK QOBILİYATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA QO‘LLANILADIGAN METODLAR. In *International conference on multidisciplinary science* (Vol. 2, No. 2, pp. 68-70).